

The chlorophyll content, plant height, and biomass were measured. Rice was harvested at maturity, and its yield recorded (Table 1), and characteristics analyzed (Table 2).

Spraying with PGRs promoted rice yield. The percent increase in the yield over control showed that PGR-H, CSL, and Aminos gave comparable bioefficacy.

PGRs Vipul, Paras, and 110-R are classified as long-chain aliphatic alcohols; CSL, Aminos, and PGR-H as modified amino acids. A correlation between these characteristics and bioefficacy suggests that the latter PGRs promote larger biomass and more chlorophyll, which lead to efficient photosynthesis and higher productivity.

The number of sprays (nine) used in the experiment was high to establish the utility of PGRs; dose and frequency of spraying still need to be optimized.

Rice from higher yielding PGRs was analyzed for nutritional and commercial characteristics (Table 2). Most of the nutritional characteristics were comparable, except for an increase in protein content, which is highly desirable. Reduced breakability during polishing

Table 1. Chlorophyll content, leaf dry weight, plant height, and yield profiles of rice sprayed with various PGRs, Patiala, India.^a

Plant growth regulator	Chlorophyll		Dry leaves		Height		Yield		
	mg/g	±SD	g	±SD	cm	±SD	kg	±SD	Increase (%) over control
PGR-H	1.55	0.04	1.19	0.03	112	4.0	25.4	2.4	41
CSL	1.34	0.05	1.11	0.05	103	3.0	25.1	1.7	39
Aminos	1.32	0.05	1.12	0.04	106	4.7	24.5	2.0	36
Vipul	1.17	0.03	1.02	0.05	98	8.3	24.0	3.3	33
110-R	1.22	0.01	1.04	0.01	100	6.3	21.0	1.8	17
Paras	1.18	0.01	1.04	0.00	102	2.3	20.4	2.3	13
Control	1.10	0.02	1.01	0.03	98	6.2	18.0	3.2	-

^aData from 30 samples (10/plot).

Table 2. Nutritional and commercial characteristics of rice grain.

Plant growth regulator	Characteristic (%)						
	N	Protein	Minerals	Moisture	Water ^a	Germination	Breakables
PGR-H	1.3	8.1	0.4	9.2	4.0	92	17
CSL	1.4	8.8	0.5	9.8	4.2	92	25
Aminos	1.3	8.1	0.5	9.3	4.3	93	21
Control	1.1	6.9	0.5	9.2	3.9	89	17

^aEstimated as residual dry weight after soaking 100 g in 500 ml demineralized water for 16 h at ambient temperature.

also has commercial significance.

Large-scale PGR spray trials in various agroclimatic zones and using

different rice varieties are suggested to establish PGR utility for increasing rice production. ■

A path coefficient analysis of rice panicle traits

J. Ramalingam, N. Nadarajan, C. Vanniarajan, and P. Rangasamy, Agricultural Botany Department, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai 625104, Tamil Nadu, India

We evaluated the effects of panicle characters on grain yield in 20 high-yielding genotypes during rabi (Sep-Jan) 1991-92. We planted the genotypes in three rows of 10 plants each at 20- × 10-cm spacing in a randomized block design with three replications. Panicle

traits and grain yield were recorded for the main tillers of 10 randomly selected plants for each entry in each replication. We used path coefficient analysis to assess the direct and indirect influence of various panicle characters on grain yield.

Direct (underlined) and indirect effects of panicle traits on grain yield in rice^a, Tamil Nadu, India, 1991-92 rabi.

Character	Panicle length	No. of primaries	No. of secondaries	Primary length	Secondary length	Filled grains/primary	Filled grains/secondary	Chaffy grains/primary	Chaffy grains/secondary	Total filled grains	Total chaffy grains	Genotypic correlation with yield
Panicle length	<u>-0.263</u>	-0.137	-0.492	0.285	0.074	-0.252	0.156	-0.054	-0.245	1.828	-0.176	0.724**
No. of primaries	-0.146	<u>-0.246</u>	-0.483	0.118	0.009	0.175	0.212	-0.087	-0.166	1.469	-0.350	0.505*
No. of secondaries	-0.193	-0.177	<u>-0.671</u>	0.252	0.036	-0.214	0.264	-0.105	-0.404	2.082	-0.107	0.763**
Primary length	-0.213	-0.083	-0.481	<u>0.351</u>	0.083	-0.409	0.100	0.016	-0.204	1.858	-0.232	0.787**
Secondary length	-0.129	-0.015	-0.160	0.194	<u>0.150</u>	-0.223	-0.016	-0.066	-0.187	0.757	0.141	0.445*
Filled grains/primary	-0.107	0.070	-0.232	0.232	0.054	<u>-0.618</u>	-0.059	-0.007	-0.260	1.250	0.207	0.530*
Filled grains/secondary	0.108	0.137	0.467	-0.093	0.006	-0.097	<u>-0.380</u>	0.071	0.276	-0.844	0.087	-0.261
Chaffy grains/primary	0.031	0.046	0.152	0.012	-0.022	0.010	-0.059	<u>-0.463</u>	0.760	-0.464	-1.220	-0.291
Chaffy grains/secondary	0.078	0.049	0.327	-0.087	-0.034	0.194	-0.126	0.425	<u>0.829</u>	-1.020	-1.136	-0.502*
Total filled grains	-0.210	-0.158	-0.611	0.286	0.050	-0.338	0.140	-0.094	-0.370	<u>2.284</u>	-0.103	0.875**
Total chaffy grains	-0.034	-0.063	-0.053	0.060	-0.015	0.094	0.024	0.412	0.687	0.171	<u>-1.370</u>	-0.087

*, ** = significant at 5 and 1% levels, respectively.

Grain yield had high positive significant association with all of the characters except filled grains of secondary branches, chaffy grains of primary branches, and total chaffy grains (see table). Among the panicle traits, total filled grains, primary length, and secondary length showed both positive association as well as direct effect on yield. Number of secondary branches and panicle length had significant positive

correlation with yield, but they exhibited negative direct effect on yield.

The indirect effects of panicle length, number of primary and secondary branches, primary length, secondary length, and number of filled grains of primary branches through total filled grains were found to be very high and positive. Number of filled grains of secondary branches had a negative direct effect on yield and negative correlation

with yield, while secondary length had a positive correlation with yield.

Filled grain should be emphasized because of high positive correlations, very high direct effects, and positive indirect effects on yield through many traits. Plant type for high yield in rice should have lengthy panicles, a high number of filled grains, and long primary and secondary branches. ■

Pest resistance—diseases

Geographical distribution of varieties resistant to rice tungro disease (RTD)

R. C. Cabunagan and H. Koganezawa, IRRI

A rice viruses data base (RVDB), developed at IRRI in 1990, organizes information about resistance to RTD, rice ragged stunt virus, and rice grassy stunt virus. The system enables researchers to access current information about rice accessions that have been evaluated for virus resistance and are stored in the International Rice Germplasm Center (IRGC).

Analysis of the updated data for RTD resistance in the RVDB showed that 15,795 accessions (20.5% of the IRGC collection) had been tested before 1989 for RTD resistance as infection rate. Among them, 560 (3.5%) are resistant (less than 30% infection).

Most of the resistant varieties originated in South Asia, particularly in Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan (see table). Of the 273 resistant varieties from India, 259 were ARC lines; 32 of the 63 varieties from Pakistan were Basmati lines. Although the percentage of resistant accessions from Indonesia is low, some important resistant varieties, such as Utri Merah, Utri Rajapan, and Balimau Putih, originated in this country.

We used the mass screening method to evaluate untested varieties originating from Bangladesh, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka. Of the 3,656 accessions tested, 355 (9.5%) are resistant to RTD. The results show that a higher percentage of

resistant materials was obtained when mass screening was concentrated on varieties originating from a particular

Frequency count of accessions resistant to RTD, by geographical region.

Origin	Tested (no.)	Resistant	
		no.	%
1963-89			
East Asia	946	4	0.4
Southeast Asia	5,274	52	1.0
Cambodia	63	0	0.0
Indonesia	1,517	25	1.6
Laos	753	0	0.0
Malaysia	361	7	1.9
Myanmar	811	2	0.2
Philippines	878	10	1.1
Thailand	393	2	0.5
Vietnam	497	6	1.2
South Asia	7,590	490	6.5
Bangladesh	2,956	149	5.0
Bhutan	33	0	0.0
India	3,101	273	8.8
Nepal	40	1	2.5
Pakistan	758	63	8.3
Sri Lanka	702	4	0.6
West Asia	125	3	2.4
Africa	1,275	9	0.7
South America	161	0	0.0
North and Central America	226	1	0.4
Oceania	20	0	0.0
Europe	27	0	0.0
Unknown	151	1	0.7
Total	15,795	560	3.5
1990-91			
South Asia			
Bangladesh	2,150	263	12.2
Pakistan	283	18	6.4
Sri Lanka	1,223	79	6.5
Total	3,656	360	9.8

country of origin rather than on varieties at random.

Evaluation of untested varieties originating from India and Indonesia is in progress. ■

Effect of plant age on IR-BB21 resistance to *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (Xoo)

M. Mazzola and J. E. Leach, Plant Pathology Department, Kansas State University (KSU), Manhattan, KS 66506; T. W. Mew, IRRI; and F. F. White, Plant Pathology Department, KSU, Manhattan, KS 66506, USA

Genetic resistance is the most effective and economic means of controlling bacterial blight (BB) of rice caused by Xoo. The dominant resistance locus *Xa-21* was identified in the wild rice *Oryza longistaminata*, and the near-isogenic line IR-BB21 was generated by introducing this locus into IR24. This locus was previously reported to confer resistance to all Philippine races of Xoo. We evaluated the ability of the *Xa-21* locus to confer resistance to the BB pathogen in both seedlings and adult rice plants.

Seeds at two stages during the development of IR-BB21 (GSK80 and IR-BB21) were collected on two occasions to ensure cultivar authenticity. IR-BB10 (carrying *Xa-10*), IR-BB21 (carrying *Xa-21*), and IR24 were grown in the greenhouse at about 30/25 °C (day/night) temperatures.

Strains PXO99A (azacytidine-resistant derivative of PXO99, race 6) and PXO86 (race 2) of the Philippine Xoo isolate were grown for 48 h in terrific broth, a bacterial culture medium used for